

FAIR Software: Interactive Introduction

SORSE Workshop 17 & 19 November, 2020

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Where are you joining us from today?

germany

home

netherlands

australia

france

greece

brisbane

What is the position / job title in your e-mail signature?

Research Software Skills Specialist

eScience Research Engineer

postdoc

Open science officer

eResearch officer

Assistant Prof

research assistant

Research engineer and metadata specialist

Researcher

What is the position / job title in your e-mail signature?

Community manager

Why did you choose to join this workshop?

I care about policy that leads to better research

Feel responsible for RS, but have limited insight.

An international session scheduled during my work day! Astounding!

interested in the community discussion about FAIR and software

Learn more about FAIR4RS initiatives to push this in our own group and institution

Trying to answer the question "what is FAIR for software"

Projects are related to FAIR

Are you familiar with the FAIR data principles?

Recap: FAIR data principles

- Findable (metadata and data should be easy to find)
- Accessible (users need to know how they can be accessed)
- Interoperable (data needs to be integrated with other data, and interoperate with analysis code)
- Reusable (metadata and data should be well-described to facilitate reuse)
- See also <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

"(Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier." Which FAIR principle?

"(Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards." Which FAIR principle?

"(Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol." Which FAIR principle?

"(Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data." Which FAIR principle?

FAIR

Findable
Accessible
Interoperable
Reusable

2016: "The FAIR guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship" (Wilkinson et al., doi:10.1038/sdata.2016.18)

2018: "Central to the realization of FAIR are **FAIR Digital Objects, which may represent data, software or other research resources.**" (European Commission)

But: **How do the FAIR Principles relate to software?**

Mismatch between the broad intentions of the **4 foundational FAIR principles** and how the **15 FAIR Guiding Principles** are communicated and perceived.

What is data?

Information unprocessed

observations

data is a resource to be acted on

An observation of any kind

defined pieces of information

A representation of an observation

information in a digital format

digital representation of
information/facts/statements.

Information

What is data?

a digital object

the reason why we program
databases and search engines

What is software?

instructions

Set of algorithms

